

Kinetics of Oxidation of Iodide Ion by Iron(III) in the Presence of 2,2'-Bipyridyl

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2,2'-Bipyridyl accelerates the reaction between iron(III) and iodide ion and the kinetics of this reaction has a different pattern from that of the uncatalysed reaction. The reaction obeys first order kinetics with respect to Fe^{III} and a plot of $k'/[\text{I}^-]$ vs $[\text{I}^-]$ is linear with positive intercept, showing that the reaction has two rate-determining paths, one involving one iodide ion and the other two iodide ions. The hydrogen ion inhibits the reaction. A mechanism involving 1 : 2 iron^{III}-bipyridyl complex as the active species has been proposed.

THE oxidation of iodide ion by Fe^{III} has attracted considerable attention of the workers^{1,2}. In an earlier study, Fudge and Sykes¹ reported a complicated rate law for the reaction, according to which the reaction obeys near first order and second order kinetics in Fe^{III} and I^- , respectively, and the reaction is inhibited by Fe^{III} ion. Later, Laurence and Ellis² reinvestigated the reaction over a wider concentration range and found first order kinetics in Fe^{III} and second order kinetics in I^- . These authors, unlike Fudge and Sykes¹, proposed an outersphere complex $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}, \text{I}^-]$ which oxidises I^- .

The oxidation of iodide by tris(1,10-phenanthroline)iron(III) was reported, and in this case the reaction was found to be first order with either reactant³. It is interesting to study the kinetics of oxidation of iodide by iron(III) in presence of 2,2'-bipyridyl or 1,10 phenanthroline where the tris-complex is not formed (by direct mixing), but a labile brown complex⁴ is formed between iron(III) and this ligand. Hence, a kinetic study of this reaction, taking bipyridyl as ligand, was undertaken. It was observed that bipyridyl has a marked catalytic effect on the reaction. Under these conditions, it was found that the reaction obeys entirely different kinetic pattern. Whereas in uncatalysed reaction, only one rate-determining path was proposed for electron-transfer², the results obtained for the present reaction unambiguously show the existence of two rate-determining processes.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. The course of the reaction was followed by measuring the optical density of one of the products, trisbipyridyliron(III) complex, at 510 nm. At this wavelength, all other materials had negligible absorption. The hydrogen ion concentration in each run was adjusted to the required value with

standard 0.1 M HClO_4 with the help of a pH meter. The concentrations of the reactants and H^+ ions were always such that the uncatalysed reaction proceeds to a negligible extent. The rate constant of the uncatalysed reaction was found to be $2.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}$, whereas under the same experimental conditions, *i.e.* $[\text{KI}] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{HClO}_4] = 7.9 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}] = 7.52 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, methanol 22% (v/v), $\mu = 0.014 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Bipy}] = 6.0 \times 10^{-8} \text{ M}$, $\text{Temp.} = 30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$, the rate constant for the catalysed reaction was found to be $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The concentration of $[\text{I}^-]$ was kept at least five times greater than that of Fe^{III} to avoid the complication due to I_3^- formation. The concentration of bipyridyl is at least twenty five times greater than Fe^{III} and under these conditions the charge transfer complex formation between I_3^- and bipyridyl, if any, can only have negligible effect.

Results and Discussion

The reaction was found to obey first order kinetics in Fe^{III} under the conditions, $[\text{I}^-], [\text{Bipy}] \gg [\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}]$ as shown by the straight line plots obtained when $\log(A_\infty - A_t)$ was plotted against time, where A_∞ and A_t are the absorbances at infinite time and at time t , respectively. Linearity was persistent at least upto 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constant (k') was calculated from the slopes of these linear plots. The value of k' was found to be insensitive to variation of Fe^{III} in the range of concentrations employed. Under these isolation conditions (k') was determined at various initial concentrations of iodide ion. The type of dependence of rate on [iodide] is shown by the linear plot (Fig. 1) with a positive intercept, between $k'/[\text{I}^-]$ vs $[\text{I}^-]$. This indicates that the rate law is a sum of two terms with differing iodide dependence in each term. Thus the first term is linear in [iodide] where the second term has a square dependence on [iodide].

Fig. 1. Plot of $k'/[I^-]$ vs $[I^-]$; $[Fe^{III}] = 7.52 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[H^+] = 7.9 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Bipy] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $\mu = 0.014$ mol dm^{-3} , methanol = 22% (v/v), temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[Bipy]^2$; $[Fe^{III}] = 7.52 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[I^-] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$, $[H^+] = 7.9 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $\mu = 0.014$ mol dm^{-3} , methanol = 22% (v/v), temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

An interesting kinetic pattern was also noticed from a detailed kinetic study, varying bipyridyl concentration but keeping all others constant (Table 1). The pK value of bipyridyl⁵ is in the order of 10^{-4} , and hence all bipyridyl can be assumed to be in the protonated form, $[HBipy^+]$, even at the smallest $[H^+]$ employed. A plot of $1/k'$ vs $1/[Bipy]^2$ was linear with a positive intercept (Fig. 2) in the range of $[H^+]$, $7.9 \times 10^{-3} - 17.9 \times 10^{-3} M$. These observations indicate the presence of denominator with two or more terms, in the rate law.

TABLE 1—BIPYRIDYL EFFECT ON THE OXIDATION OF IODIDE BY Fe^{III} -2,2'-BIPYRIDYL COMPLEX

$[I^-] = 4 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[HClO_4] = 7.9 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Fe^{III}] = 7.52 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , methanol = 22% (v/v), $\mu = 0.014$ mol dm^{-3} , Temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$

$[Bipy] \times 10^3$ mol dm^{-3}	$k' \times 10^3$ min $^{-1}$
5.0	0.86
6.0	1.10
7.0	1.20
8.0	1.30
11.0	1.50
14.0	1.63
16.0	1.73
20.0	1.72

Effect of $[H^+]$ on rate: The pseudo-first order rate constant, k' was determined in the $[H^+]$ range $7.9 \times 10^{-3} - 17.9 \times 10^{-3} M$ (Table 2). The hydrogen ion was found to have inhibitory effect. In the

$[H^+]$ range $7.9 \times 10^{-3} - 17.9 \times 10^{-3} M$, a plot of $1/k'$ vs $[H^+]^2$ was found to be a straight line with a positive intercept (Fig. 3). Since only very low concentrations of iron(III) were employed ($\approx 10^{-5} M$), the dimeric form of iron(III) can be neglected. Since the hydrolysis constant of iron(III)^{6,7} has a value of 9.0×10^{-4} , the concentration of the hydrolysed form is very small even at the lowest hydrogen ion concentration employed.

Fig. 3. Plot of $1/k'$ vs $[H^+]^2$; $[Fe^{III}] = 7.52 \times 10^{-5}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[I^-] = 4.0 \times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3} , $[Bipy] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm^{-3} , $\mu = 0.014$ mol dm^{-3} , methanol = 22% (v/v), temp. = $30.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF HClO₄ ON THE OXIDATION OF IODIDE BY Fe^{III}-2,2'-BIPYRIDYL COMPLEX

[I⁻] = 4.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, [Fe^{III}] = 7.52 × 10⁻⁵ mol dm⁻³,
 [Bipy] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, methanol = 22% (v/v),
 μ = 0.014 mol dm⁻², Temp. = 30.0 ± 0.1°

[HClO ₄] × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	k' × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
7.9	1.29
9.9	1.17
11.9	1.04
13.9	0.95
15.9	0.85
17.9	0.75

Nature of reactive species: Iron(III) on direct mixing with 2,2'-bipyridyl gives rise to 1 : 2 brown complex. This is different from the tris-complex of iron(III) which can be obtained only on the oxidation of the corresponding iron(II) complex⁴. The brown complex is known to exist in both mononuclear and binuclear forms⁵. Since low concentrations of iron(III) are employed, it is logical to assume a mononuclear complex Fe(bipy)₂³⁺ to be the active oxidising species.

Lawrence and Ellis⁶ proposed that an outer-sphere complex Fe³⁺ and I⁻, rather than the inner-sphere one is formed which oxidises iodide ion. In the present case, there is greater justification in proposing an outer-sphere complex between Fe(Bipy)₂³⁺ and I⁻, in view of the bulkiness of the bipyridyl ligand. Thus the first path involves rate-determining intramolecular electron-transfer in this complex, and the second path involves an electron-transfer between this outer-sphere complex and iodide ion which explains the participation of 2I⁻ in the transition state shown by the second order dependence on I⁻ in this path. Thus the following mechanism is capable of explaining all the results.

The step (7) depicted as a fast step was also invoked by Fudge and Sykes¹. The rate law derived for

the above mechanism using equilibrium technique is given by

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}^{III}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Fe}^{III}] [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2} + \frac{k_2 K_2 K_3 [\text{Fe}^{III}] [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2}$$

Under the conditions [Bipy], [I⁻] ≫ [Fe^{III}], the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' is given by

$$k' = \frac{k_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2} + \frac{k_2 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2} \quad (I)$$

Taking reciprocals, one gets

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+]}{k_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-] + k_2 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]^2} + \frac{1}{k_1 K_3 [\text{I}^-] + k_2 K_3 [\text{I}^-]^2} \quad (II)$$

$$\frac{k'}{[\text{I}^-]} = \frac{k_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2} + \frac{k_2 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]}{[\text{H}^+]^2 + K_1 [\text{H}^+] + K_2 [\text{Bipy}]^2} \quad (III)$$

Equation (III) requires that a plot of k'/[I⁻] vs [I⁻] should be a straight line with positive intercept, which in fact has been obtained (Fig. 1). Further, a plot of 1/k' vs 1/[Bipy]² must be also a straight line with positive intercept, which was also observed (Fig. 2).

The value of K₁ was reported^{6,7} to be 9 × 10⁻⁴ and hence K₁[H⁺] can be neglected in comparison with [H⁺]² even at the lowest acidity employed (7.9 × 10⁻³ M). Hence, equation (II) undergoes modification to

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{k_1 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-] + k_2 K_2 K_3 [\text{Bipy}]^2 [\text{I}^-]^2} + \frac{1}{k_1 K_3 [\text{I}^-] + k_2 K_3 [\text{I}^-]^2} \quad (IV)$$

According to equation (IV), plots of 1/k' vs [H⁺]² and 1/k' vs 1/[Bipy]² should be linear with positive intercepts. Such linear plots were observed in the [H⁺] range 7.9 × 10⁻³ – 17.9 × 10⁻³ M. Further, the values of the intercepts were found to be nearly the same as required by the rate law, lending further support to it. The value of K₂ was calculated to be 2.45 from the slopes and intercepts of these plots and using equation (IV). From the slope and intercept of the plot of k'/[I⁻] vs [I⁻] and from the knowledge of K₂, the overall rate constants of paths (4) and (5), k₁K₂ and k₂K₂ were calculated to be 70.5 mol⁻¹ l min⁻¹ and 11.8 × 10⁴ mol⁻² l² min⁻¹, respectively. Using these values, the apparent activation energies were calculated to be 48.9 and 96.3 kJ mol⁻¹, respectively. However,

these rate constants, involve the equilibrium constant K_8 also, whose value can not be determined from the kinetic study.

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